

Schmidt Ocean Institute Post Expedition Report

Costa Rican Deep Sea Connections

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1 Overview

SOI Expedition ID	FK190106
Vessel	R/V <i>Falkor</i>
Expedition Name	Costa Rican Deep Sea Connections
Expedition Dates	2019/01/06 - 2019/01/27
Departure Port	Puntarenas, Costa Rica
Termination Port	Puntarenas, Costa Rica
Ocean	Pacific Ocean

1.0.0.1 Map of Expedition Location

Figure 1: Map of Expedition Location.

1.1 Expedition Overview

The deep sea is home to a variety of understudied ecosystems that need better human understanding if they are to have any protection from encroaching deep-sea fishing and mining activities. These systems support the global marine environment through habitat creation, nutrient cycling, and maintenance of biodiversity. However, they are also found in areas with rich stores of oil, gas, minerals, and potential new pharmaceuticals. Understanding what ecosystem processes generate these key services is fundamental to their protection.

The Pacific margin of Costa Rica is an area of seamount subduction where methane seeps, thermal anomalies, and non-subducting seamounts intersect and presumably interact. Despite several research expeditions to this region, scientists knew very little about how these ecosystems may be connected to communities in the rest of the ocean, including the soft-sediment background communities and deep-sea corals. To characterize these interactions, the expedition used a sampling framework that coupled benthic sampling, near-bottom chemical sensor and photographic profiling, along with vertical characterizations through the water column from deep to shallow.

1.2 Authorizations and Permitting

Permit Number	Permit Authority	Permit Focus
R-070-2018-0T	CONGAGEBIO	Access to genetic and biodiversity elements
CPI-003-12-2018	INCOPESCA	Access to genetic and biodiversity elements
DVMP-DNS-2018-1144	Ministry of Foreign Affairs	Navigation & Docking in Costa Rican Waters

Table 1. List of obtained permits and their focus.

1.3 Expedition Timeline

The expedition began on January 6, 2019, departing from Puntarenas, Costa Rica, and returned on January 27, 2019, to Puntarenas, Costa Rica.

1.4 Expedition Objectives

This expedition was a continuation of the ROC HITS (Research On Cold seeps and How they Influence The Sea) program funded by the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF). The overarching goals of the NSF program were to examine the sphere of influence of cold seeps on the surrounding deep-sea ecosystem, using the high-flux

seeps of the Costa Rica Margin as a case study. The extent of the physical, chemical, and biological connections between habitats was revealed through a combination of oceanographic measurements, community specimen collections, and the study of population genetics, stable isotope tracers, microbial diversity, and biogeochemistry. A series of manipulative experiments were also conducted to test specific hypotheses about the influence of seepage on community structure.

The work on board *Falkor* continued some of the program's studies on the seeps and expanded them to include a series of seamounts further offshore. These seamounts influence the community structure and connectivity throughout the region. For example, they serve as a control for the availability of hard substrata in the absence of seepage and local chemosynthetic productivity. In addition, the previous surveys of the seamounts represented the first descriptions of these habitats and communities, which furthered efforts to conserve these habitats between the near-shore marine protected areas and the offshore Isla del Coco National Park within Costa Rican waters.

2 Expedition Accomplishments

2.1 At-sea Accomplishments

2.1.1 Overview

Operations for this expedition involved ROV dives, CTD casts, Wire Flyer deployments, and multibeam echosounder surveys. The ROV dives included collecting specimens, targeted water sampling, using push cores, and transplanting carbonates between habitat types. CTD casts were conducted over specific sites to obtain water samples to verify other oceanographic measurements obtained by sensors. The Wire Flyer is a towed vehicle that conducts rapid vertical profiling of the water column using a suite of sensors, utilized during the short transits between sites. Multibeam bathymetry data were obtained over many of the seep and seamount sites that had not been previously surveyed.

At each site, a series of samples were taken to assess the community structure and the biogeochemistry of the habitats. Representative samples of as many species as possible were collected. Collections were deposited at the University of Costa Rica and some specimens were deposited at the Scripps Institution of Oceanography. Sufficient numbers of gastropod and crustacean species were collected to conduct population genetics and morphometric analyses. The other major sampling effort was in the push cores for sediment sampling, which were processed in numerous ways, including for macrofauna identifications and stable isotope studies, looking for novel symbioses in the macrofauna, microbial community characterization in the sediments, and examination of geochemical flux rates in the sediments. In particular, studies were focused on the role of Xenophyophores, giant single-celled protists, in the deep-sea community.

The scientists dedicated eight ROV dives to exploring the seamounts along the transect out to Isla del Coco. These samples collected on these dives provided excellent comparative samples to examine the deep-sea community, since there was not a lot of hard substrata found beyond the seeps along the continental margin. The deep-sea corals and other fauna collected from the hard substrate were collected and compared to the seep communities, providing reference data to communities from a similar range of depths. Besides the work with ROV *SuBastian*, the “Wire Flyer” survey vehicle was employed.

2.1.2 Science

Specimen collections

There were 634 individual samples obtained during the cruise. These included a wide variety of fauna collected individually, by suction sampler, in push cores, and from carbonate rocks. The complete list of faunal samples can be found in the Data section below (Table 2).

A comprehensive list of all fauna, plus hundreds of new DNA sequences, collected on this and previous cruises, was published in [Zookeys](#) (Seid et al. 2025). A comprehensive look at the gastropods of the region was also published in a series of papers (Betters et al. 2023, 2024).

Characterizing Methane Seeps and Seamounts

The characterization of methane seeps was continued from previous cruises in 2017 and 2018 on the R/V *Atlantis*. Together, these surveys have resulted in a greatly improved characterization of the fauna, habitat, geochemical conditions, and biogeography of the seep environment in the region. Mound Jaguar was also visited, which the scientists had tried to explore previously, but never had the proper ocean conditions.

Mapping

The seamount chain that runs between the Costa Rica Margin and Isla del Coco had never been mapped by shipboard echosounder. During the expedition, six of these seamounts and more of the area in the vicinity of the Isla del Coco protected area were mapped.

2.1.3 Innovative Technologies

The Wire Flyer has now become established as a standard oceanographic tool, but at the time of the cruise in 2019, it was still under development. This expedition significantly contributed to refining the deployment methods and utilization for water column profiling. The vehicle was deployed ten (10) times to collect data on the vertical cross-sections of the water column overlying the seeps and seamounts, using a suite of

chemical sensors (temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, pH, turbidity, fluorometry, and oxidative-reductive potential) and forward-looking echosounders.

2.2 Post-Expedition Activities and Accomplishments

2.2.1 Overview

Using many of the samples from this cruise, results have been shared that examine the extent of the seep influence on the surrounding deep sea. This is a scientific question that has been unanswered for years, and researchers today have a better understanding of these patterns. In addition to the published results, two Ph.D. dissertations from Temple University have also contributed to this scientific question; one is complete (April Stabbins) and another is close to completion (Emily Cowell) at the time of report publication.

During the cruise, a series of incubations were conducted to test whether deep-sea corals (*Swiftia sahlungi*) were capable of taking up some of the carbon from the methane seeps we were investigating. Once these stable isotope label data were examined, there was conclusive evidence that the corals were utilizing the seep food supply. This is the first time that the direct uptake of methane-derived carbon has been demonstrated for a coral species of any kind. At the time of this report, the resulting manuscript is under revision (Stabbins AL, Goffredi SK, Gasbarro R, Dawson KS, Magyar JS, Glazier A, Orphan VJ, Meinert K, Cordes EE. Microbially mediated carbon usage by a deep-sea methane seep coral. In revision for ISME Communications).

As part of the expedition, a series of social media blogs and images was well-received, with nearly 600 followers. In addition, one of the SOI blog posts included a video of cutlassfish in the water column that was viewed over 250,000 times. There was also a series of interactions with English- and Spanish-speaking classrooms. More directly, the Vice Minister for the Environment of Costa Rica, along with the head of Conservation International in Costa Rica joined on board for a tour and a discussion about deep-sea conservation. The science party also had the opportunity to visit Isla del Coco National Park and host the rangers from the park on board for a tour and dinner.

In the years following the cruise, Costa Rica greatly expanded the area of the Isla del Coco marine protected area. This is largely credited to the exploration of the seamounts in the vicinity of the island that occurred during this cruise, and the subsequent outreach efforts.

2.2.2 New Discoveries and Species

The biological specimens collected during this expedition have been deposited at (1) the Zoology Museum at the School of Biology of the University of Costa Rica (MZUCR) and

(2) the Benthic Invertebrate Collection at the Scripps Institution of Oceanography (SIO-BIC) in La Jolla, California, USA. This expedition resulted in the collection of 634 biological samples (many consisting of more than one species at a time), including deep-sea corals, annelid worms, yeti crabs, and other crustaceans, bivalves, gastropods, echinoderms, and sponges. The specimens at MZUCR and SIO-BIC will serve as reference vouchers for ecological and genetic studies, such as the potential description of new species. Sample observed specimens are shown in Figure 2 below. The specimens will support fundamental biodiversity research, enrich the education of undergraduate and graduate students, and contribute to public education at MZUCR and SIO-BIC.

Figure 2.a: *Peinaleopolynoe mineoi* - hungry scale worm

Figure 2.b: *Bathymodiolus billschneideri* – mussel

Figure 2.c: *Bathymodiolus earlougheri* - mussel

Figure 2.d: *Bathymodiolus nancyschneiderae* - mussel

Figure 2.e: *Laminatubus paulbrooksi* - tubeworm

Figure 2.f: *Laminatubus joycebrooksae* - tubeworm

Figure 2.g: *Pyrolycus Jaco* - eelpout fish

Figure 2.h: *Munidopsis cortesi* - squat lobster

Figure 2.i: *Munidopsis girguisi* - squat lobster

Figure 2.j: *Pectinereis strickrotti* - polychaete

Figure 2: Sample biological specimen observed during the expedition.

2.3 Data

Datasets acquired during this expedition and those derived from the analysis of collected data and samples as of this report's publication date.

Data Type	Curator	Completed
Vessel underway data	Rolling Deck to Repository	Yes
Biodiversity Data	iDigBio and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility	Yes
Georeferenced Species Abundance	Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO)	Yes
Voucher Specimens	Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office (BCO-DMO)	Yes
Collected Samples	Scripps Benthic Invertebrate Collection (SIO-BIC)	Yes
Genetic Data	GenBank/NCBI	Yes
Raw Illumina 16S rRNA Barcode Sequences and Metadata	Dryad and NCBI	Yes
ADCP data	University of Hawaii SOEST	Yes
Data collected by ROV <i>SuBastian</i> including CTD, photography, navigation, and event logging	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Yes
Processed MBES Data	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Yes
ROV Imagery	Squidle+	Yes
<i>Bathymodiolus billschneideri</i> Species Description	World Register of Marine Species	Yes
<i>Bathymodiolus earlougheri</i> Species Description	World Register of Marine Species	Yes

<i>Bathymodiolus nancyschneiderae</i> Species Description	World Register of Marine Species	Yes
Holotype information from the new species of squat lobster described <i>Munidopsis cortesi</i>	Scripps Benthic Invertebrate Collection	Yes
Sediment cores and carbonates geochemistry: All geochemistry (porewater, isotopic, and cell count data) from sediment cores and carbonates		No

Table 2. List of all publicly available data

2.4 Publications

Frable, Benjamin W., Charlotte A. Seid, Allison W. Bronson, and Peter Rask Møller. 2023. "A New Deep-Sea Eelpout of the Genus *Pyrolycus* (Teleostei: Zoarcidae) Associated with a Hydrothermal Seep on the Pacific Margin of Costa Rica." *Zootaxa* 5230 (1): 79–89. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5230.1.5>.

Goffredi, Shana K., Ekin Tilic, Sean W. Mullin, Katherine S. Dawson, Abigail Keller, Raymond W. Lee, Fabai Wu, et al. 2020. "Methanotrophic Bacterial Symbionts Fuel Dense Populations of Deep-Sea Feather Duster Worms (Sabellida, Annelida) and Extend the Spatial Influence of Methane Seepage." *Science Advances* 6 (14): eaay8562. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aay8562>.

Grassian, Benjamin, Christopher Roman, Joseph D. Warren, and Dave Casagrande. 2023. "High-Resolution Measurements of the Epipelagic and Mesopelagic Ocean by a Profiling Vehicle Equipped with Environmental Sensors and a Broadband Echosounder." *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods* 21 (2): 106–25. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lom3.10532>.

Hiley AS, Mongiardino Koch N, Rouse GW. Phylogenetics of Lepidonotopodini (Macellicephalinae, Polynoidae, Annelida) and Comparative Mitogenomics of Shallow-Water vs. Deep-Sea Scaleworms (Aphroditiformia). *Biology*. 2024;13(12):979. doi:10.3390/biology13120979.

Hiley, Avery S., Nicolás Mongiardino Koch, and Greg W. Rouse. 2024. "Phylogenetics of Lepidonotopodini (Macellicephalinae, Polynoidae, Annelida) and Comparative Mitogenomics of Shallow-Water vs. Deep-Sea Scaleworms (Aphroditiformia)." *Biology* 13 (12): 979. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology13120979>.

Levin, Lisa A., and Greg W. Rouse. 2020. "Giant Protists (Xenophyophores) Function as Fish Nurseries." *Ecology* 101 (4): e02933. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.2933>.

McCowin, Marina F., Patrick C. Collins, and Greg W. Rouse. 2023. "Updated Phylogeny of Vestimentifera (Siboglinidae, Polychaeta, Annelida) Based on Mitochondrial Genomes, with a New Species." *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 187 (October): 107872. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2023.107872>.

McCowin, Marina F., Caitlin Feehery, and Greg W. Rouse. 2020. "Spanning the Depths or Depth-Restricted: Three New Species of *Bathymodiolus* (Bivalvia, Mytilidae) and a New Record for the Hydrothermal Vent *Bathymodiolus Thermophilus* at Methane Seeps Along the Costa Rica Margin." *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers* 164 (October): 103322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr.2020.103322>.

Mongiardino Koch, Nicolás, Ekin Tilic, Allison K. Miller, Josefin Stiller, and Greg W. Rouse. 2023. "Confusion Will Be My Epitaph: Genome-Scale Discordance Stifles Phylogenetic Resolution of Holothuroidea." *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 290 (2002): 20230988. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2023.0988>.

Pereira, O., Jacobsen, M., Carson, R., Cortes, J., and Levin, L. (2024). Understanding and valuing human connections to deep-sea methane seeps of Costa Rica. *Ecol. Econ.* 223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2024.108228>.

Rodríguez-Flores, Paula C., Charlotte A. Seid, Greg W. Rouse, and Gonzalo Giribet. 2023. "Cosmopolitan Abyssal Lineages? A Systematic Study of East Pacific Deep-Sea Squat Lobsters (Decapoda: Galatheoidea: Munidopsidae)." *Invertebrate Systematics* 37 (1): 14–60. <https://doi.org/10.1071/IS22030>.

Rojas-Jimenez, Keilor, Hans-Peter Grossart, Erik Cordes, and Jorge Cortés. 2020. "Fungal Communities in Sediments Along a Depth Gradient in the Eastern Tropical Pacific." *Frontiers in Microbiology* 11 (November). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.575207>.

Rouse, Greg W., and Elena K. Kupriyanova. 2021. "Laminatubus (Serpulidae, Annelida) from Eastern Pacific Hydrothermal Vents and Methane Seeps, with Description of Two New Species." *Zootaxa* 4915 (1): 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4915.1.1>.

Sagorny, Christina, Jörn von Döhren, Greg W. Rouse, and Ekin Tilic. 2022. "Cutting the Ribbon: Bathyal Nemertea from Seeps Along the Costa Rica Margin, with Descriptions of 2 New Genera and 9 New Species." *European Journal of Taxonomy* 845 (October): 132–74. <https://doi.org/10.5852/ejt.2022.845.1959>.

Seid, C., Hiley, A., McCowin, M., Carvajal, J., Cha, H., Ahyon, S., Ashford, O.Rouse, Greg W. (2025). A faunal inventory of methane seeps on the Pacific margin of Costa Rica. *Zookeys* 1222: 1-250. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1222.134385>.

Villalobos-Guerrero, Tulio F., Sonja Huč, Ekin Tilic, Avery S. Hiley, and Greg W. Rouse. 2024. "A Remarkable New Deep-Sea Nereidid (Annelida: Nereididae) with Gills." *PLOS ONE* 19 (3): e0297961. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0297961>.

3 Appendix

3.1 Science Party Information

Scientist	Institution
Erik Cordes	Temple University
Oliver S. Ashford	Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San Diego
Steve Auscavitch	Boston University
Jorge Cortés-Núñez	University of Costa Rica
Shannon Dwyer	Temple University
Ben Grassian	University of Rhode Island
Avery Hatch	Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San Diego
John Magyar	California Institute of Technology
Beatriz Naranjo-Elizondo	University of Costa Rica
Lisa Levin	Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San Diego
Allison Miller	University of Otago
Alon Philosofof	California Institute of Technology
Greg Rouse	Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San Diego
Russell Coffield	
Mónika Naranjo-Shepherd	MarViva

Table 3. List of scientists and students aboard *Falkor*.